

PREDICT 6G

D5.1

Data Management Plan

UC3M

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Abstract

This document is the Data Management Plan for the PREDICT-6G project. The purpose of this document is the establishment of project documentation standards and a full set of project procedures to meet the highest quality level of the project outcomes.

The document describes the data management life cycle for the data to be collected, processed and/or generated by PREDICT-6G, to make research data findable, accessible, interoperable, and re-usable (FAIR).

Keywords

Data Management Plan, results, FAIR,

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Document information

Nature of the deliverable [R]

Dissemination level

PU Public, fully open. e.g., website ✓

CL Classified information as referred to in Commission Decision 2001/844/EC

SEN Confidential to PREDICT-6G project and Commission Services

* Deliverable types:

R: document, report (excluding periodic and final reports).

DEM: demonstrator, pilot, prototype, plan designs.

DEC: websites, patent filings, press and media actions, videos, etc.

OTHER: software, technical diagrams, etc.

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Table of partners

SHORT NAME	PARTNER
UC3M	<u>Universidad Carlos III de Madrid</u>
NOK	Nokia Solutions and Networks KFT
ERC	<u>Ericsson España SA</u>
INT	<u>Intel Deutschland GMBH</u>
TID	<u>Telefónica Investigación y Desarrollo SA</u>
ATOS	<u>ATOS IT Solutions and Services Iberia SL</u>
GES	<u>Gestamp Servicios SA</u>
NXW	<u>Nextworks</u>
COG	<u>Cognitive Innovations Private Company</u>
SIM	<u>Software Imagination & Vision SRL</u>
AUSTRALO	<u>AUSTRALO Alpha Lab MTU</u>
POLITO	<u>Politecnico di Torino</u>
UPC	<u>Universitat Politecnica de Catalunya</u>
CNR	<u>Consiglio Nazionale delle Ricerche</u>
UNIPD	<u>Universita degli Studi di Padova</u>
IDE	<u>Interdigital Europe LTD</u>

Executive summary

The Data Management Plan (DMP) describes the involved data in the PREDICT-6G project.

The purpose of the DMP is to provide an overview of all datasets collected and generated by the project and to define the consortium's data management policy that is used with regard to these datasets. The DMP follows the structure of the Horizon Europe DMP template. It reflects the status of the data that is collected, processed, or generated and following what methodology and standards, whether and how this data will be shared and/or made open, and how it will be curated and preserved. This initial version of the DMP defines the general policy and approach to data management in PREDICT-6G that handles data management related issues on the administrative and technical level.

Acronyms

AI	Artificial Intelligence
DMP	Data Management Plan
DoA	Description of the Action
DOI	Data Object Identifier
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Re-usable
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
KPI	Key Performance Indicators
ML	Machine Learning
SLAM	Simultaneous Location and Mapping
WP	Work Package

1 Introduction

The document describes the data management life cycle for the data to be collected, processed and/or generated by a Horizon 2020 project, to making research data findable, accessible, interoperable, and re-usable (FAIR).

As per Annotated Grant Agreement [1], DMP outlines the main aspects of the lifecycle of research outputs, notably including data, i.e., provenance, organisation and curation, as well as adequate provisions for their access, preservation, sharing, and eventual deletion, both during and after a project.

This document is structured as follows: first there is a description of the related data in PREDICT-6G project. Second, it provides a description of the FAIR usage of data. Third, resources are allocated for data management and finally ethical aspects are discussed.

PREDICT-6G project partners will use this DMP as a compulsory reference for data management within the project. Each project partner will be responsible and must make sure that the generated and handled data is treated according to the provisions of this DMP.

All the project partners have been introduced to the DMP and its use as part of WP5 activities. Relevant questions and concerns from partners will also be addressed within WP5. This DMP will be updated through the project duration whenever there are relevant clarifications to consider.

2 Data Summary

The structure of DMP follows the parameters to be clarified regarding the management of the project's generated data. Following the template recommended by the EC [2], DMP includes the following major components:

- ☐ FAIR Data
- ☐ Other research outputs
- ☐ Allocation of resources
- ☐ Data security

It is the responsibility of each consortium partner to ensure the data generated by the partner is treated according to the details laid out in this DMP.

The approach proposed in the current DMP is based on an initial assessment of data handling procedures and anticipated datasets. Each consortium partner has filled-in the questionnaire below.

Q1	Will you generate or re-use any existing data and what will you generate/re-use it for? State the reasons if re-use of any existing data has been considered but discarded.	What is the expected size of the data that you intend to generate or re-use?
Q2	How will you provide documentation needed to validate data analysis and facilitate data re-use (e.g., readme files with information on methodology, codebooks, data cleaning, analyses, variable definitions, units of measurement, etc.)? Will you re-use any existing data and what will you re-use it for? State the reasons if re-use of any existing data has been considered but discarded.	Describe all relevant data quality assurance processes.
Q3	In addition to the management of data, beneficiaries should also consider and plan for the management of other research outputs that may be generated or re-used throughout their projects. Such outputs can be either digital (e.g. software, workflows, protocols, models, etc.) or physical (e.g., new materials, antibodies, reagents, samples, etc.).	Beneficiaries should consider which of the questions pertaining to FAIR data above, can apply to the management of other research outputs, and should strive to provide sufficient detail on how their research outputs will be managed and shared, or made available for re-use, in line with the FAIR principles.
Q4	What will the costs be for making data or other research outputs FAIR in your project (e.g., direct and indirect costs related to storage, archiving, re-use, security, etc.)?	How will these be covered? Note that costs related to research data/output management are eligible as part of the Horizon Europe grant (if compliant with the Grant Agreement conditions)

Q5	What provisions are or will be in place for data security (including data recovery as well as secure storage/archiving and transfer of sensitive data)?	
Q6	Are there, or could there be, any ethics or legal issues that can have an impact on data sharing? These can also be discussed in the context of the ethics review. If relevant, include references to ethics deliverables and ethics chapter in the Description of the Action (DoA).	Will informed consent for data sharing and long-term preservation be included in questionnaires dealing with personal data?
Q7	Do you, or will you, make use of other national/funder/sectorial/departmental procedures for data management? If yes, which ones (please list and briefly describe them)?	

The information and data that is expected to be generated by the PREDICT-6G consortium include the following three types of data:

1. **Human readable documents:** project documentation, research documentation, publications etc. [typical office document formats, e.g., predominantly in the ‘Portable Document Format’ (PDF)].
2. **Source code** and software binaries: for implementation of functionalities, support of experimentation and simulation [plain text, binary software formats].
3. **Experimental data:** raw data from experiments and processed statistical data [raw data].

Regarding the Experimental data, during the project lifetime data will be reused from other sources and new data will be generated. For data sources already available, the project plans to reuse the following:

- ☐ Existing datasets¹ of robot manipulator remote control use case that performs a pick and place task. The dataset will be used for training analytical models, extracting traffic with deterministic requirements, and AI/ML mechanisms for prediction and orchestration.
- ☐ Research datasets already existing for KPI evaluation. These will be used in standard format such as text files and results in a sample form e.g., .csv files. This source will be made available by the partners of the consortium, who generated it in the past.
- ☐ Public sources such as IEEE Data Port (<https://iee-dataport.org/>) or any other online publicly available dataset.

The Project will also generate original datasets, specifically we plan to:

- ☐ Generate datasets of mobile robot performing SLAM (Simultaneous Location and Mapping) and autonomous navigation using lidar and camera. The data will contain the mobile robot odometry, the

¹ Existing dataset comprise all the data – both research data (primary research results data) and scientific / technical data (research outputs, peer-reviewed publications) - generated prior to project PREDICT-6G.

lidar scans, the camera scans, and the obtained point to the cloud. We will also provide rosbags² to recreate the data collection process. This data will be used for training AI/ML models for point cloud prediction.

- ☐ Generate datasets of network traffic and network characteristics based on emulation/simulation and direct collection from test sites.

These data sets are important for the project since a key pillar for PREDICT-6G and its concept of determinism is the prediction of the network state. The project aims at devoting substantial effort to create novel AI-based forecasting and prediction algorithms leveraging network digital twins. The creation of such prediction module requires large amounts of data to train and validate the Artificial Intelligence (AI) / Machine Learning (ML) algorithms. PREDICT-6G takes a strong data-driven approach based on both synthetic yet representative data considering expected system behaviours and will collect traces from real equipment.

The data generated within the project will be useful in the future for the development of:

- ☐ AI algorithms for prediction: The data will be useful for research groups and 3rd party application developers.
- ☐ Datasets for KPI evaluation from use cases: The data will be useful for potential customers, EU regulatory and policymakers to assess the impact of the PREDICT-6G solutions.

3 FAIR Data

PREDICT-6G Consortium follows the principle of FAIR data and so this section of the Data Management Plan describes how the project makes sure its data is findable, accessible, interoperable and reusable. Interested parties might be internal project researchers, or the public in general.

3.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

To make PREDICT-6G data findable, standard dataset names and full metadata and descriptions will be provided as it is described in the next section.

PREDICT-6G data sets will be evaluated for open access; firstly if it is desirable and secondly, if it can be provided. Where such an evaluation is positive, data sets will be made available online via research data sharing platforms; Zenodo is identified as the primary option. In addition to the standard metadata, Zenodo includes assignment of a Digital Object Identifier (DOI), sophisticated versioning and licensing/access control.

² ROSBAG, Jun. 2023, [online] Available: <http://wiki.ros.org/rosbag>

The associated metadata will contain the keywords associated with the dataset. Document metadata is information assigned to a document to provide additional context. This metadata describes such characteristics as what the document is, who created it and when it was created.

Applying metadata to documents can help ensure information accuracy, simplify document search and retrieval, and automate business processes using an enterprise content management system.

At the end of the project, the coordinator will create a static copy of the web site of the project, including the information on all Open Science activities, storing it in the Internet Archive and on the UC3M servers/cloud used for these purposes. Data sets used for training AI will be made discoverable through Zenodo ElasticSearch and accessible depending on the level of confidentiality associated to the data set.

We will tag our results using the Metadata format used by Zenodo³, which can be exported as MARCXML, Dublin Core, and DataCite Metadata Schema. We will also consider the creation of an OpenAire Community Gateway for the research associated, together with the rest of projects funded.

To ease the finding of our results, we will use a nomenclature for each of the results as follows. For code storage we will use a hybrid approach, we will store the code currently under development in a temporal internal repository, while for each release we will store it also in Zenodo as an immutable version of the code repository.

Data Set Reference and Name

Multiple data types will be generated within the PREDICT-6G project with different data sets and requirements. However, the data sets of all data types will follow a common naming scheme. The suggested naming scheme is as follows:

PREDICT-6G_[Type]_[Name]_[Date]_[Partner]_[Version], where:

- ❑ [Type] is the type of data, as described in the previous section (i.e., publication, code, design, experimental);
- ❑ [Name] is a short and characteristic name for the data. Mainly for experimental data, the name could include two-digit number to identify data generated by the same partner in the same day. The number designation will start by 00 and will increase in cardinal order;
- ❑ [Date] is the date when data was produced (format: YYYYMMDD);
- ❑ [Partner] is the name of the organization associated with the dataset, as per the partner acronyms at the beginning of this document.
- ❑ [Version] is the numbering of versions of the data;
- ❑ _ (underscore) is used as the separator between the fields.

For example, the following name of a potential data set: PREDICT-6G_experimental_data_20230419_UC3M_v1 would identify a data set of the type of experimental data.

³ <https://zenodo.org/schemas/records/record-v1.0.0.json>

The data set is generated on 19-04-2023 by UC3M (which is thus the owner of the data set) and the current data set is the first version.

Data Set Description and Metadata Standards

A data set for the purpose of this DMP is considered to consist of one or multiple files and associated metadata as well as a description of the data set. A data set may combine files of multiple data types. The description and metadata of the dataset serve the purpose of identification, description and guidance for use and will at least contain the following information, fulfilling the requirements of the Dublin Core metadata schemas/standards:

- ❑ Identifier(s): an identifier, optionally, additional unique identifiers (e.g., DOI for publicized data sets, a deliverable number of project deliverables etc.).
- ❑ Creator/Author: name(s) and affiliation(s).
- ❑ Title: title of the data set.
- ❑ Publisher: the entity publishing the data set.
- ❑ Date: the year and month of publication, optionally the day and time of day.
- ❑ Type: the dataset type, as defined below.
- ❑ Format: the format(s) of the included data.
- ❑ Description: a description of the data set, including description of its origin and intended use.

Data Sharing and Preservation

The sharing and preservation of data sets generated in PREDICT-6G are highly dependent on the data type. A priori it is within the responsibility of each consortium partner to maintain and preserve the data generated at their side. A collaboration and sharing platform (Microsoft SharePoint) has been set up to allow collaborative creation and sharing of data sets containing predominantly human readable documents. The data sets deposited and created on this sharing platform are stored and preserved by the coordinator.

Additional requirements and strategies for sharing and preservation of data sets from some data set types or more specific groups of data sets with specific circumstances have been agreed and are summarized below.

Project Data

- ❑ Description: All shared project data (work in progress documents, administrative data)
- ❑ Release: Confidential
- ❑ Access: Closed
- ❑ Sharing: SharePoint
- ❑ Preservation: SharePoint
- ❑ Responsible: Project Coordinator

Reports, dissemination and communication

- ❑ Description: Project deliverables, publications, project reports, project communications
- ❑ Release: Public
- ❑ Access: Open
- ❑ Sharing: Teams, EC participant portal, project website
- ❑ Preservation: EC participant portal
- ❑ Responsible: Project Coordinator, authors (publications)

Design data

- ❑ Description: Design data in open access
- ❑ Release: Public
- ❑ Access: Open
- ❑ Sharing: Zenodo, online sharing platforms
- ❑ Preservation: Zenodo
- ❑ Responsible: Authors/Creators

Raw research data and Analysed research data

- ❑ Description: Research data
- ❑ Release: Public
- ❑ Access: Open
- ❑ Sharing: Zenodo, online sharing platforms
- ❑ Preservation: Zenodo
- ❑ Responsible: Authors/Creators

3.2 Making data accessible

PREDICT-6G will make generated results available by using a well-known repository: Zenodo. Zenodo⁴ is an open repository for all scholarship, enabling researchers from all disciplines to share and preserve their research outputs, regardless of size or format. Free to upload and free to access, Zenodo makes scientific outputs of all kinds citable, shareable, and discoverable for the long term. A Zenodo community has been created, and all results of the project (including publications) will be linked to it.⁵

⁴ <https://zenodo.org>

⁵ <https://zenodo.org/communities/predict-6g/>

Zenodo assigns all publicly available uploads a DOI to make the upload easily and uniquely citeable. Zenodo further supports harvesting of all content via the OAI-PMH protocol, and all metadata is available through a CC license.

To broaden the dissemination and availability of results, PREDICT-6G will rely on complementary open access channels including: (i) The release of pre-publication versions through the website; (ii) The release of paper presentations in conferences through the website; (iii) The use of social media to provide links to publications and presentation files. Other "lighter" publications, for example, conference and workshop contributions, will also be provided with Open Access, likely through a 'green' approach using e.g., arXiv.org or other appropriate repositories. Similarly, deliverables produced by the project will also be archived in stable repositories, to ensure the long-term availability of the material. Archiving of the deliverables may be done with an embargo period, in coordination with the EC office.

PREDICT-6G is based on the concept of openness, and that vision can become reality only if Open Science (including open-source) policies are fully embraced. As such, it's the project default policy for sharing results is to make them as much as possible public. Due to the participation of large companies in the project, there will be some results that will remain closed for some time (embargo). The length of the embargo period will be defined on a per-result basis. Currently, for the specific results needing it, we aim at defining an embargo time of 6 months after the finalization of the project to allow protection of all results. All project results will be available in Zenodo (commitment to have a copy of the result in Zenodo before 2 months after the generation of the result, for non-confidential results).

In case some results (data set, code, etc.) cannot be made public due to exploitation reasons, metadata will be generated and stored in Zenodo to easily spot and retrieve such results.

Data will be shared using standard formats. So far, we have not identified the need of any specific software for accessing the data. All code generated by the PREDICT-6G project will be released by using open-source licenses.

3.3 Making data interoperable

It is PREDICT-6G's aim to make its data interoperable to the maximum degree possible without impacting the execution of work and research within the consortium and where possible within reasonable effort. To make data exchange possible, standard formats, vocabularies and document structures will be applied. Zenodo uses JSON Schema as internal representation of metadata and offers export to other popular formats such as Dublin Core or MARCXML. For certain terms we refer to open, external vocabularies, e.g.: license (Open Definition), funders (FundRef) and grants (OpenAIRE). We do not anticipate the use of any project-specific ontology or vocabulary.

3.4 Increase data re-use

PREDICT-6G aims at increasing the data re-use by publishing everything in standard formats and providing the instructions needed to recreate the experiment or re-process the data. Documentation on how to reuse the project results will be made available in the Zenodo community, per selected result. When possible, we will provide the scripts used to process project data or replicate the experiments. Depending on the nature of the result, we will use (as much as possible) open licensed such as EPL-v2.0 or CC-BY. Dataset published in the PREDICT-6G project will be made available through recommended dataset repositories to ensure the long-time access of the data.

Quality assurance procedures will be established as part of the management tasks, organizing at least three peer reviews for each deliverable to guarantee the scientific and editorial quality of the submitted documents. The Open Science and Output Manager will review in a periodic basis that all results are made available in Zenodo.

4 Other research outputs

The project has already identified in the previous sections what different types of material will be generated. Basically, all the research outputs are subject to be included in Zenodo, even source code. The working copy of the source code will be managed in a GitLab repository. Once a certain release is ready to be shared with the public, we will link it to Zenodo, creating a specific static copy of it in the GitLab repository.

Finally, for all outputs generated we will follow the FAIR principles, and specifically all outputs will include information on the dissemination level intended, the mandatory metadata and specific metadata including instructions on how to replicate the results.

5 Allocation of resources

The archiving and preservation of project data is mainly the responsibility of the consortium partner generating the data. For data made publicly accessible, different provisions are made within the consortium.

In addition, UC3M will allocate one person, the Open Science and Output manager (Sandra Álvarez, UC3M, female), in charge of making sure output management and open science methodologies are followed and that all results are available following the FAIR philosophy.

During the project preparation phase, every partner has been allocated a certain number of resources to be able to comply with the Open Science directive.

6 Data security

All data generated will be stored at least in two places: (i) in the PREDICT-6G SharePoint, and (ii) in Zenodo.

The Project SharePoint is managed by UC3M which follows the strictest security protocols on its digital operations. In addition, the SharePoint content is backed up daily to an out of premises server, through an encrypted connection and using a password-based storage. This ensures the security of data.

Zenodo, as a project from the European Commission is considered a Trusted Repository, meeting all possible security directives for the management of data.

7 Ethics

As stated in the project plan: “No ethics issues have been entered in the ethical issues table in the administrative proposal forms”. PREDICT-6G information collected can be released without privacy restrictions because it does not constitute private information about identified human subjects. The project will monitor if ethical or privacy implications arise and use a general strategy for the monitoring of the implications.

Should ethical implications arise, the project shall follow the GDPR [3] Act on the protection of natural persons regarding the processing of personal data and on the free movement of such data.

8 Other issues

The project will not use any other procedures for the management of data apart from the ones listed in this document.

9 References

- [1] AGA. (2023). *Annotated Grant Agreement: V1.0 DRAFT– 01.04.2023*. EU Grants.
- [2] EC. (2021). *Data Management Template (HE):V1.0*. EC.
- [3] GDPR. (2016). *Regulation (EU) 2016/679 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 27 April 2016 on the protection of natural persons with regard to the processing of personal data and on the free movement of such data.*

10 ANNEX 1 – DMP questionnaire

10.1 Data Summary

	Will you generate or re-use any existing data and what will you generate/re-use it for? State the reasons if re-use of any existing data has been considered but discarded.	What is the expected size of the data that you intend to generate or re-use?
UC3M	<p>We will reuse existing datasets of robot manipulator remote control use case that performs a pick and place task. The dataset contains the robot will be used for training of analytical model, AI/ML mechanisms for prediction and orchestration. In case of KPI evaluation, dataset will use standard format such as text files and results in a sample form e.g., .csv files).</p> <p>We will generate datasets of mobile robot performing SLAM and autonomous navigation using lidar and camera. The data will contain the mobile robot odometry, the lidar scans, the camera scans, and the obtained point to the cloud. We will also provide rosbags to recreate the data collection process. This data will be used for training AI/ML models for point cloud prediction. The dataset will use standard formats such as text files and results in a sample form e.g., csv.</p>	Unclear at the moment
NOK	No reuse of existing data is planned.	N/A
ERC	No reuse of existing data is planned.	N/A
INT	No reuse of existing data is planned.	N/A
TID	No reuse of existing data is planned.	N/A

ATOS	ATOS do not plan to reuse any existing data. Data used in the project will be either obtained from internal simulation-based data generators or made available by other PREDICT-6G partners for developing different functionalities as part of the control and management plane.	Data size will depend on several parameters related to the design of the control and management plane, data plane technologies considered, etc.
ATOSP	ATOS do not plan to reuse any existing data. Data used in the project will be either obtained from internal simulation-based data generators or made available by other PREDICT-6G partners for developing different functionalities as part of the control and management plane.	Data size will depend on several parameters related to the design of the control and management plane functionalities, data plane technologies considered, etc.
IDE	<p>InterDigital do no plan to use existing data. If data from outside of PREDICT-6G is used, it is obtained from public sources such as IEEE Data Port or any other online resource under well-defined usage rights.</p> <p>On the generation of data, InterDigital plan do collect, store and process data from various OSI layers on UEs, gNBs, and Core Networks. This data is used for enhancing RAN and CN system behaviours using AI/ML. No personalised user data will be collected, stored or processed other than for conducting experiments, demos or trials where users may have to create username and password on a temporary basis.</p>	InterDigital is not bound by any file size to work on the AI-domain.
GES	No reuse of existing data is planned. The idea is to acquire the data from the UEs (robots, PLCs, etc.) from the use case.	The size of the data will depend on the amount of type functionality generated by the UEs
NXW	Nextworks do no plan to use existing data. Potentially Nextworks will generate data through emulation in its own lab making use of open-source sw for 5G Core network and simulators of RAN traffic, open-source tools for data plane traffic generation and shaping, combining them with data collected from computing nodes in Nextworks lab.	N/A
COG	No reuse of existing data is planned.	N/A

SIM	We will reuse data and code from open-source initiatives and internal resources. The data sets will use standard formats (text, csv, etc).	Depends on the input from other partners.
AUS	Some of the data generated will be used for communication and dissemination purposes, including the elaboration of different materials project-related.	N/A
POLITO	POLITO will both use existing datasets that are widely used for training of machine learning (ML) models and generate datasets that can help tailor ML models to time-critical services and applications. Part of such datasets will also be used for decision-making processes (i.e., inference operations).	The size of the datasets will depend on the type of devices that will be considered for hosting training and inference processes based on ML models.
UPC	No reuse of existing data is planned.	N/A
CNR	CNR and UNIPD do not plan to use existing data. Probably we will generate data through emulations or simulations in its own laboratories making use of open-source software for TSN networks and real/emulated robots as traffic generators.	The size of the generated dataset will depend on the type of experiments and devices emulated/simulated.

10.2 FAIR Data

Increase data re-use

	How will you provide documentation needed to validate data analysis and facilitate data re-use (e.g. readme files with information on methodology, codebooks, data cleaning, analyses, variable definitions, units of measurement, etc.)? Will you re-use any existing data and what will you re-use it for? State the reasons if re-use of any existing data has been considered but discarded.	Describe all relevant data quality assurance processes.
UC3M	Readme files with all required information and documentation will be available on the project website and GitHub repository.	Different quality assurance processes will be applied depending on the nature of the data set.
NOK	Readme files with the required information uploaded to the project website and GitHub repository.	The quality assurance process will depend on the type of output produced.
ERC	Readme files with all required information and documentation will be available on the project website and GitHub repository.	According to the project guidelines
INT	Readme files with all required information and documentation will be available on the project website and GitHub repository.	According to the project guidelines
TID	Readme files with all required information and documentation will be available on the project website and GitHub repository.	According to the project guidelines
ATOS	Readme files with the required information will be uploaded to the project website and GitHub repository.	Quality assurance will depend on the nature of the data set.
ATOSP	Readme files with the required information will be uploaded to the project website and GitHub repository.	Quality assurance will depend on the nature of the data set.

IDE	<p>The documentation to validate data analysis and facilitate data re-use will be provided via text- and image-based representations on a platform accessible to all parties in the data creation, storage and processing chain.</p> <p>If existing data sets have been considered but discarded, it is very likely</p>	<p>All data collected will be stored as occurred and any post-processing or clean-up will take place without affecting the originally stored data. Furthermore, each data set stored will be accompanied with a clear description of the scenario where it was collected or better re-suability.</p>
GES	<p>Documentation will be provided, if necessary, in readme text. Also images will be available to project website and repository</p>	<p>Data will be collected, processed and stored following project criteria.</p>
NXW	<p>Readme files with all required information and documentation will be available on the project website and GitHub repository.</p>	<p>Pre-processing and validation criteria still to be identified.</p>
COG	N/A	N/A
SIM	<p>Documentation will be made available in readable formats</p>	<p>QA procedures specific for different types of data</p>
AUS	<p>The communication and dissemination deliverables and materials will be published in Zenodo and the project website.</p>	<p>The quality assurance process will depend on the type of output produced.</p>
POLITO	<p>Readme files with the required information will be uploaded to the project website and GitHub repository.</p>	<p>Different quality assurance processes will be applied depending on the nature of the data set and the scenario for whose assessment the dataset will be used.</p>
UPC	<p>Readme files with the required information will be uploaded to the project website and GitHub repository.</p>	<p>Data will be collected, processed and stored following project criteria.</p>
CNR	<p>For CNR and UNIPD, readme text files with the necessary information will be uploaded to the project website and GitHub repository.</p>	<p>The type of output generated will determine the quality assurance process.</p>

10.3 Other research outputs

	In addition to the management of data, beneficiaries should also consider and plan for the management of other research outputs that may be generated or re-used throughout their projects. Such outputs can be either digital (e.g. software, workflows, protocols, models, etc.) or physical (e.g., new materials, antibodies, reagents, samples, etc.).	Beneficiaries should consider which of the questions pertaining to FAIR data above, can apply to the management of other research outputs, and should strive to provide sufficient detail on how their research outputs will be managed and shared, or made available for re-use, in line with the FAIR principles.
UC3M	For all potential research outputs, we will provide documentation (readme file). Dataset published in the project will be made available through recommended dataset repositories to ensure long-time access of the data.	Depending on nature of results, documentation on how to reuse the result will be available in the web page related to the result in the project web site.
NOK	All research outputs will be documented and shared via the project website or GitHub repository.	Documentation for the research outputs will be included.
ERC	All research outputs will be provided using the project public structure	According to project policies
INT	N/A	N/A
TID	N/A	N/A
ATOS	Research outputs will be documented and shared via the project website or GitHub repository.	Documentation for the research outputs will be included.
ATOSP	Research outputs will be documented and shared via the project website or GitHub.	Documentation for the research outputs will be included.
IDE	InterDigital fully adheres to the consortium agreement where the	N/A
GES	All outputs will be documented and uploaded in project website and repository	Documentation for research outputs will be included.

NXW	All research outputs will be documented and shared via the project website or GitHub.	Documentation for the research outputs will be included.
COG	N/A	N/A
SIM	<p>The outputs generated (software) will follow closely FAIR principles.</p> <p>In case of research data, we will specify:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The dissemination level (P, SEN, EU-R) - Mandatory metadata: EU, HORIZON, GA 101095890, PREDICT-6G <p>Specific metadata: reference information used to edit WPxx reports, comprising a collection of literature and their related impact analyses</p>	<p>FAIR principles will be considered when coding as follows:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - FINDABLE : use of metadata, persistent identifiers, - ACCESSIBLE: standard communication protocols, open free protocols - INTEROPERABLE: using vocabularies <p>REUSABLE: provenance, usage licence</p>
AUS	The communication and dissemination deliverables and materials will be published in Zenodo and the project website.	N/A
POLITO	All research outputs will be documented and shared via the project website or a proper publicly accessible repository.	Documentation for the research outputs will be included.
UPC	All research outputs will be documented and shared via the project website or a proper publicly accessible repository.	Documentation for the research outputs will be included.
CNR	The findings of the research will be documented and disseminated through either the project website or an appropriate publicly accessible repository.	Documentation for the research outputs will be included.

10.4 Allocation of resources

	What will the costs be for making data or other research outputs FAIR in your project (e.g., direct and indirect costs related to storage, archiving, re-use, security, etc.) ?	How will these be covered? Note that costs related to research data/output management are eligible as part of the Horizon Europe grant (if compliant with the Grant Agreement conditions)
UC3M	UC3M has allocated PMs and specific cost to cover the figure of Open Science Manager	Grant
NOK	N/A	N/A
ERC	N/A	N/A
INT	N/A	N/A
TID	N/A	N/A
ATOS	N/A	N/A
ATOSP	N/A	N/A
IDE	The cost for storing digital and analogue data is considered to be covered by the 25% overhead, as InterDigital has strict procedures for that in place already.	The publication of data sets on platforms such as IEEE Data Port is considered and will be charged
GES	N/A	N/A
NXW	N/A	N/A
COG	N/A	N/A
SIM	Direct and indirect costs	All the costs anticipated at this point are eligible to be claimed as part of GA
AUS	N/A	N/A
POLITO	N/A	N/A
UPC	N/A	N/A

CNR	N/A	N/A
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10.5 Data security

	What provisions are or will be in place for data security (including data recovery as well as secure storage/archiving and transfer of sensitive data)?
UC3M	Personal data will be stored in a private repository. Zenodo or GitHub will be used as a certified repository for ensuring the long-term preservation of the data. No sensitive data will be used or generated.
NOK	No sensitive data will be used or generated.
ERC	No sensitive data will be used or generated
INT	N/A
TID	N/A
ATOS	No sensitive data will be used or generated.
ATOSP	No sensitive data will be used or generated.
IDE	Any data (public information from InterDigital's standpoint) generated by InterDigital will be shared via secure technologies, e.g. U3CM's Microsoft SharePoint.
GES	No sensitive data will be used or generated.
NXW	No sensitive data will be used or generated.
COG	N/A
SIM	EN ISO 27001:2013 Standards governing copyright, literature database licensing / subscription agreements and common ethical principles
AUS	N/A
POLITO	No sensitive data will be used or generated.

UPC	No sensitive data will be used or generated.
CNR	No sensitive data will be used or generated.

10.6 Ethics

	Are there, or could there be, any ethics or legal issues that can have an impact on data sharing? These can also be discussed in the context of the ethics review. If relevant, include references to ethics deliverables and ethics chapter in the Description of the Action (DoA).	Will informed consent for data sharing and long-term preservation be included in questionnaires dealing with personal data?
UC3M	There won't be any ethical issue since we will not work with human-related data. In addition to this, in case of accessing potentially sensitive data, it will be treated according to Horizon Europe Ethics and Data Protection guideline by considering GDPR.	Yes
NOK	N/A	N/A
ERC	N/A	N/A
INT	N/A	N/A
TID	N/A	N/A
ATOS	N/A	N/A
ATOSP	N/A	N/A
IDE	N/A	N/A
GES	No ethic or legal issues are expected	Yes
NXW	N/A	N/A
COG	N/A	N/A
SIM	N/A	N/A

AUS	No ethic nor legal issues are expected since all the activities will follow the adequate procedures (mainly GDPR)	Yes
POLITO	N/A	N/A
UPC	No ethic nor legal issues are expected since all the activities will follow the adequate procedures (mainly GDPR)	Yes
CNR	N/A	N/A

10.7 Other issues

	Do you, or will you, make use of other national/funder/sectorial/departmental procedures for data management? If yes, which ones (please list and briefly describe them)?
UC3M	No
NOK	N/A
ERC	No
INT	N/A
TID	N/A
ATOS	No
ATOSP	No
IDE	No
GES	No
NXW	No
COG	N/A
SIM	Internal procedures are in line with national/international norms.

AUS	N/A
POLITO	No
UPC	No
CNR	No